

Simulation of visitor flows management in the Slovenian coastal zone using the technology of the urban digital twin

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Abstract

Cities are complex systems that require efficient data management in terms of daily information on tourist flows and other elements of spatial mobility. In this context, many professional discussions address the need to improve the conventional spatial planning system in light of the current challenges of a new society. Technological innovations and approaches such as Urban Digital Twins represent useful tools that allow detailed analysis and visualization of visitor flow in different scenarios. With this research, the aim is to find out the applicability of such an innovative approach in the process of spatial planning. Understand visitor flows as a complex system of interactions that take place along specific paths in the urban environment and depend on the mobility of tourism and the capacity of existing infrastructure. At the same time, this technology allows for the identification of the behavioral patterns of individual agents with the spatial configuration of the coastal area. In this way, it is possible to plan measures to avoid conflicts caused by coastal overcrowding. A theoretical and simulation approach that integrates visitor behavior patterns is used to represent the dynamic characteristics of digital twins. The concrete case study was conducted in individual zones of the Slovenian coastal zone. A simulation of visitor flows and short-term mobility, determined by pedestrian flows and road traffic flows, was created. This approach creates a framework

for urban planners and other interest groups in the direction of a better understanding and use of new technological tools in optimizing urban spatial planning.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

https://youtu.be/BHGh0eQK_9c

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